

INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO WRITING PROBLEMS OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Turg'unboyeva Shahnoza

The student of UzSWLU

Phone number: +998949236792

Email: shakhnozabaxtiyarovna@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785120>

Annotation: In this thesis, the issues of providing solutions to several problems related to the formation of writing skills encountered by university students are considered.

Key words: essay writing, vocabulary, idea generation, grammar structures, spelling errors, assessing process.

We are aware that one of the most crucial and pressing challenges in any university's instructional process is the development of writing skills. When it comes to other talents, writing poses a number of difficulties for students. This is due to a number of factors. For instance, the ability to write demands that students think independently, approach the assigned material subjectively, and come up with unique ideas that no one else has. For most pupils, this is really challenging. Their limited perspective, little experience, and insufficient information from other areas exacerbate the difficulties of writing. Take, for instance, the assignment of writing an essay for a foreign language university's midterm and final test. Students are taught the essay writing process in detail, from practical to theoretical, prior to these tests. A midterm control is given to the students to test them after they have worked on each section for multiple lessons. You can assign the task of writing a letter at beginning to make it easier. Writing a letter follows a set format, structure, and sequence even though it doesn't take much imagination. It takes some talent on the part of the learner to write a letter using this template and communicate the information that has been transmitted. The procedure of composing an essay comes next. In this, pupils are asked to display actual inventiveness talents. Students will be assigned this kind of essay topic. They will be required to produce a predetermined amount of essays on this subject. The essay's content should be created so that it is unique, matches the topic, and is written in a variety of ways that take into consideration all factors, which are relevant to the writing process.

This is where students start to encounter a series of issues. Of course, the first obstacle in starting the process is the lack of a novel and unique idea. Many scientists and educators propose a way of reading books as a remedy for this. Reading a book inherently broadens one's perspective, regardless of whether it is an artistic or scientific work written in Uzbek, English, or Russian. We can succeed greatly in the essay's section involving the presentation of facts and proof if we broaden our life experiences by reading scientific publications and by experiencing the events depicted in artistic works. English essays tend to be more realistic and follow a predetermined format, whereas Uzbek essays place greater emphasis on artistic expression. Thus, integrating the reading of creative and scientific works might help to tackle one of the main issues with the essay-writing process. We have the option to employ contemporary methods and technologies as our second alternative. For instance, locating films and documentaries about our subject on websites and social media these days, as well as developing the capacity to make inferences and consider the subject from several angles, will all be

beneficial when composing an essay. Particularly in the essay's main body, the explanation of the concept backed up by specific instances and data demonstrates a high level of intellectual capacity and understanding of current events.

Despite of these issues, there are other aspects that we should not overlook. According to Hedge (1988), there are a few things that students should keep in mind when using the product writing method. These include: a) Structure and format b) Correct spelling c) Vocabulary variety d) Proper grammar e) Intense punctuation f) Cohesive devices g) different sentence types.

Writing problems with learners According to Byrne (1988) and Hedge (1988), the author must maintain a line of discourse by selecting suitable patterns and transitions so that the text's content could be comprehended by itself. The writer must meticulously organize their writing before starting. As well as pick their words and grammatical structures. According to Byrne (1988) and Hedge (1988), learners' writing issues might take the form of grammatical issues, mechanical issues, issues with sentence structure, and diction issues.

Word-Choice problems. According to Norish (1983), good writing should include acceptable and diversified vocabularies, correct syntax, and various sentence patterns. Reid (1983) asserts that when a learner uses appropriate terminology that reflects the purpose of the writing, the material they produce may come across to the reader as logical. However, second language learners still struggle with word choice since they frequently utilize lengthy words and phrases in their writing to capture the reader's interest, White (1980). Dictation problems will eventually arise because of this. **Sentence structure problems.** According to Reid (1983), sentences can have a variety of syntactic patterns. Tsegaye (2006) contends that some learners do, however, utilize run-on, inaccurate, and fragmented phrases. According to Kharma (1986), some students are unable to create longer phrases. Conjunctions were shown to be difficult for second language learners, according to Zamel (1983).

Spelling errors. Gowere et al. (1995) believe that the impact of other languages, diverse pronunciations, and other historical factors contribute to the complexity of the English spelling system for students.

Furthermore, there are several ways to solve these problems. **The product approach** to writing focuses on the finished products of the writing work rather than the process. Nunan (1989) states that the product approach to writing focuses on the end result of the act of composition, that is the letter, essay story and so on. The writing teacher who uses the product approach will be concerned to see that the end product is readable, grammatically correct and obeys discourse conventions relating to main points, supporting details and so on. Raimes (1983:6) writes “ in the control approach of teaching writing students are given sentences to copy and manipulate grammatically and correctly with very limited opportunity of making mistakes.” Hedge (1988:8) suggests some points which students should include in the product approach of writing. These include: a. Getting the grammar right. b. Having a range of vocabulary. c. Punctuating meaningfully. d. Using the conventions of layout correctly. e. Spelling accuracy. f. Using a range of sentence structures. g. Linking ideas and information across sentences to develop a topic. h. Developing and organizing the content clearly and convincingly. **The Process Approach** to writing focuses on the composing process of writing instead of on the written final products. Encouraging students to have a sense of purpose and audience, while writing about a certain topic, is the major task of teachers who teach in line with the process

approach. Hedge (1988:9) states that good writers appear to go through certain processes which lead to successful pieces of written work. She has proposed the following steps that good writers follow in the process approach of writing.

- a) The writers start with an overall plan in their head.
- b) They think about what they want to say and who are they writing for.
- c) They then draft out sections of the writing and as they work on them, they constantly reviewing, revising and editing their work. [2;44]

In conclusion, we can say that the formation of writing skills is a difficult and continuous process, because the problems encountered in it are individual. Each student working on themselves and correcting their mistakes by getting the right advice will help him to get rid of the current problems.

References:

1. Writing skills problems: causes and solutions Bashir Elbashir. Scientific article (p.55-56)
2. University Students' english writing problems: diagnosis and remedy Dr. Ibrahim Mohamed Alfaki. Scientific article (p.44)
3. Academic Writing: Challenges and Potential Solutions Manal AlMarwani (p. 117-118)